

Intermountain Journal of Translational Medicine

Dear Colleagues, Researchers, and Students,

We are thrilled to welcome you all as we embark on an exciting new journey with *Intermountain Journal of Translational Medicine (IMJTM)*. It is an honor to introduce this academic platform dedicated to engaging and supporting early career researchers and students.

Translational medicine bridges the gap between fundamental scientific knowledge and practical application. It is a broad field where the exchange of ideas and collaboration are paramount. Thus, *IMJTM* welcomes contributions from a wide range of disciplines, including neuroscience, molecular biology, pharmacology, genetics, clinical research, bioinformatics, and public health.

We are committed to providing a supportive and inclusive environment for new researchers. We encourage submissions from researchers of diverse backgrounds and experiences and strive to embrace new perspectives that enrich our understanding of medicine and biology. At *IMJTM*, one of our primary goals is to provide an avenue for the dissemination of novel research, innovative ideas, and transformative discoveries, all while encouraging the development of the next generation of scholars.

With a rigorous peer-review process and a dedication to the scientific method, *IMJTM* seeks to publish original research articles, reviews, case studies, and more - all of which must meet our requirements for academic integrity, scientific validity, robust methodology, and high ethical standards.

We invite each of you to be part of this academic adventure, whether as an editor, author, reviewer, or reader.

Thank you for being part of the *Intermountain Journal of Translational Medicine* community. We eagerly await your contributions and support

Sincerely,

Alfred Amendolara MS, OMS-III
Co-Editor-in-Chief

John Kriak PharmD
Co-Editor-in-Chief